
Boarding School Learning Management Towards Positive Discipline of Students at MAN 1 Pesantren Darussalam Ciamis West Java

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ABSTRACT: This research is motivated by the rise of undisciplined students because of the busy schedule of activities in the dormitory, study time until late at night, midnight activities, as a result when in class students tend to be lazy because of sleepiness. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of boarding school learning patterns on the positive discipline of students, as well as how much influence boarding school learning patterns have on the positive discipline of students in senior high school in MAN Darussalam Ciamis. This research uses a quantitative approach with ex post facto method. The population in this study were high school boarding school students in Ciamis. The data collection technique uses an instrument in the form of a questionnaire. Before being used to obtain objective data, first the validity and reliability of the questionnaire was carried out. After the data is collected, then the data is processed and analyzed using the Prerequisite Test (Normality and Linearity), Simple Linear Regression Test, Hypothesis Test (t test and Determination Coefficient Test). The results of this study indicate that the boarding school learning pattern has an influence on a positive and significant effect on the positive discipline variable of students. the tcount value of 3.480 is greater than the t-table value of 1.671 with a significance value of $0.00 < 0.05$. While the adjusted R square coefficient value shows that the marketing mix has an influence of 13.5% with a calculation of $100\% - 16.5\%$, then 86.5% is another factor that affects boarding school learning patterns in high school boarding schools in MAN I Darussalam Ciamis.

KEYWORDS: learning pattern, boarding school, positive discipline

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the best tools for developing students' personalities (As'ad 2014, 251). The SISDIKNAS Law no. 20 states that education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills they need and society (Indonesia 2003).

Boarding school makes an institution not just a school, but there students can live away from home and family, so that students/santri can focus on studying and developing a sense of discipline and responsibility towards themselves in the same place. (Marsudi 2012, 44).

There are many positive values of formal learning at school --- in this case at MAN 1 Darussalam Ciamis --- as well as studying at the Darussalam Ciamis Islamic Boarding School. They not only study formal general subjects, but also learn Islamic religious knowledge with the aim of increasing worship, piety and having responsibility towards themselves, their families and society in general as well as their responsibility as a nation that loves their homeland.

Therefore, the results are very positive, especially in terms of student discipline, and in the future they will enter society in addition to experiencing general knowledge as well as practicing Islamic religious knowledge that is rahmatan lil alamin.

From many researches journals, there are advantages or benefits in implementing boarding school learning patterns, one of which is in a research journal (Muhibuddin, Parianto and Jamaluddin 2021, 11-17). There are several benefits in implementing boarding school, one of which is forming an independent personality. With the boarding school system, children are accustomed to being independent, apart from that, if learning is carried out using the boarding school system, students can easily understand and implement it directly.

Apart from the advantages or benefits of the boarding school learning pattern, there are also disadvantages, all schools that have boarding schools use a full day school system, coupled with a busy activity schedule in the dormitory, study time until late at night, midnight activities, as a result when in class students tend to lazy because sleepy. Adolescence is a bit constrained by several rules. Children sometimes feel bored so they are lazy about studying, some even become uncomfortable and ask to leave (Muhibuddin, Parianto and Jamaluddin 2021, 14)

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The dynamic nature of students' lives during their development period certainly requires that the education given to them must also be adapted to their mental condition. High School (SMA) at this level, students are experiencing a transition phase from adolescence to adulthood, in this case the search for identity. In this phase, educators must be clever in providing guidance so that a student is able to control himself because in the transition phase students are very vulnerable to negative influences (Reskiawan and Agustang 2021). So if a student's self-identity is not strong from the start, they will be very easily influenced by negative things that will hamper their future. (Hartini, 2017).

Discipline is an example of character that can make people judge someone. Discipline is the character of obeying provisions that have been mutually agreed upon, usually discipline related to time and regulations. Thomas Gordon in (Ramlafatma 2021) discipline is behavior and discipline that is in accordance with rules and regulations, or behavior that is obtained from continuous training. However, discipline is a character that is difficult to develop in Indonesian society. It is proven that in every activity there is always a delay in carrying it out, such as being late for ceremonies, being late for learning hours, and being slow in doing assignments and so on (Reskiawan and Agustang 2021).

Positive discipline is a parenting philosophy based on encouragement, empowerment, and mutual respect. Parents or educators are expected to understand that discipline is about guiding children, and not being permissive or punitive (with punishment). Positive discipline is a method where parents or educators communicate directly to children what behavior is appropriate, what is inappropriate, and what the rewards are for good behavior and the consequences for bad behavior. This method was developed by dr. Jane Nelsen, a licensed marriage, family and child counselor. Positive discipline itself is an authoritative method that focuses on encouragement and problem solving. Different from conventional methods, positive discipline does not use physical punishment, shouting, or giving children severe punishment.

The cultivation and system of disciplinary attitudes in education is not presented as an act of restraint or limitation of students' freedom to carry out actions as they wish, but as an act of directing them to a responsible attitude and having a good and orderly way of life, so that students do not feel that discipline is a burden but is a necessity for him in carrying out his daily tasks (Tu'u 2008, 33).

Several previous studies that strengthen the research that will be discussed include the results of research conducted by Annisa Husna Sabila regarding the influence of discipline in the Boarding School system on student independence. The results of the research show that the level of student discipline is "high". Of the total 42 respondents, there were 22 students in the high criteria. Meanwhile, the level of student independence is "quite high". Furthermore, there is a significant influence between the level of discipline in the boarding school system on the level of independence of class VII SMP IT Ihsanul Fikri students.

In the journal entitled the boarding school system (Bording School) in shaping the character of discipline at MAN 1 Kolaka, written by Muh Miftah Nurul Reskiawan and Andi Agustang, there are similarities in variable X and similarities in variable Y regarding discipline. The results of the research show that the implementation of the boarding school system at MAN 1 Kolaka is emphasizing rules in each student's routine, building closeness with good communication between coaches and students, having additional lesson hours. The obstacle faced in forming a disciplined character, namely coaching, is the lack of teaching staff in the dormitory, the obstacle faced by students is the lack of privacy and feeling bored. The results of implementing rules and regulations in forming a disciplined character at MAN 1 Kolaka are: reduced students breaking the rules and increased discipline (Reskiawan and Agustang 2021).

It is in harmony with research written by Muh Miftah Nurul Reskiawan and Andi Agustang, in Umi Kholidah's thesis entitled Character Education in the Boarding School System at MAN Winosari Gunungkidul Yogyakarta. The results of the research can be concluded that (1) The character education values developed in the Boarding School system at MAN Wonosari include (a) Love of God and truth, (b) Responsibility, (c) Discipline, (d) Independence, (e) Honest and trustworthy/trustworthy, (f) Respectful and polite/manners, (g) Affection/kinship, (h) Care and cooperation, (i) justice and leadership, (j) Cleanliness, (k) health, (l) ornate neatness. The aim of implementing the Boarding School program is to instill character values in depth, creating a comfortable and pleasant environment. Meanwhile, the practical implementation is in the form of situations that occur at the MAN Wonosari Boarding School, including the exemplary attitude exemplified by the Boarding School supervisors to their students by performing congregational prayers, praying together, being taught about honesty at every opportunity and others (Kholidah, Education Characters in the Boarding School System at MAN Winosari Gunungkidul Yogyakarta 2011).

In previous research, there was a boarding school system or pattern for character, especially disciplinary character, researchers specialized more in positive discipline. For the location that will be the research object, the researcher is interested in the SMA Boarding School in the city of Bandung. In the process of searching for research objects, from the results of the preliminary study there are more than 8 senior high school boarding schools in the city of Bandung, so the researcher will take 2 samples. Based on the analysis of previous research problems' and phenomena, it is necessary to conduct further studies regarding "The Influence of Boring School Learning Management Patterns on the Positive Discipline of Students in Senior High School Boarding Schools in the City of Bandung".

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METHOD

This research will use a quantitative approach, which examines variables. A quantitative approach is systematic, clear, planned research from the beginning to the end of the research. The quantitative approach is research on data collected and expressed in the form of numbers, although it also includes qualitative data as support, such as words or sentences arranged in questionnaires, sentences resulting from research interviews and informants. (Sugiyono, Quantitative, Qualitative and R&B Research Methods 2011). To find out whether or not there is a relationship between the Boarding School Learning Pattern and the Positive Discipline of Students at MAN I Darussalam Ciamis. This research will examine this relationship.

Meanwhile, the method used in this research is the ex post facto method, which means after the fact is a type of research where the researcher looks from the perspective of the past to identify the cause and effect relationship between the dependent variable and an independent variable. The population in this study were students of MAN I Pesantren Darussalam Ciamis.

Data collection techniques using questionnaires distributed to MAN 1 Darussalam Ciamis boarding school students. Variable measurement in this research uses a Likert scale. Then for data analysis then to manage this data analysis assisted by the SPSS 26 program with Instrument Test (Validity and Reliability), and the Eviews 12 SV program with Prerequisite Test (Normality and Linearity), Simple Linear Regression Test, Hypothesis Test (t test and Coefficient of Determination Test).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Boarding School Learning Patterns at MAN 1 Pesantren Darussalam Ciamis.

Boarding schools are educational institutions where students not only study, but they live and live together in the institution. Boarding schools combine parsantri/a students' residence in school institutions far from their homes and families with being taught religion and learning several subjects in the same place (Marsudi 2012, 44).

There are elements in a boarding school that can be indicators of achievement in accordance with the boarding school learning pattern in the book Handbook of Canadian Boarding Schools by Ashley Thomson and Sylvie Lafortune, published in 1999, there are eight indicators of achievement 1) A supportive learning environment, 2) Parental involvement, 3) Safety and supervision, 4) Increased independence, 5) Development of social skills, 6) Balanced life experiences, 7) Commitment to excellence, 8) Positive and inclusive environment.

The results of statistical testing show that the boarding school learning pattern at MAN I Islamic Boarding School Darussalam Ciamis obtained a mean value of 4.31 which is in the interval 4.20 – 5.00, which includes the "Very High" qualification. The boarding school learning pattern carried out by the senior high school boarding school MAN I Pesantren Darussalam Ciamis is implemented quite well, as evidenced by the results of student development in the process of implementing the boarding school learning pattern, starting from supervision, social development, to the Islamic boarding school environment.

Positive Discipline of Students at MAN I Boarding School Darussalam Ciamis.

Positive discipline is a way of teaching and guiding children by letting them know what behavior is acceptable in a firm but kind way (J. Nelsen 2013). In other words, positive discipline is a way of teaching and encouraging discipline by maintaining a balance between firm and kind. Positive discipline is not about punishment or control but about teaching, education, preparation, training, regulation, skill development by building trust, promoting self-regulation, understanding of children, a sense of empathy and focus on solutions (J. Nelsen 2013)

The following are indicators of positive discipline theory according to Jane Nelsen, namely 1) Having a different perspective on discipline, 2) Respecting children's needs and feelings, 3) Focusing on solutions, 4) Using positive language, 5) Teaching responsibility, 6) Considering age and the child's development stage, 7) Maintaining a positive connection between educators or parents and children.

The results of statistical testing show that the positive discipline of students at senior high school boarding schools throughout Bandung City obtained a mean score of 4.21 which is in the interval 4.20 – 5.00, which is included in the "Very High" qualification. The positive discipline of students carried out by high school boarding schools throughout the city of Bandung is implemented quite well, as evidenced by the results of student development in the process of development in discipline.

The Influence of Boarding School Learning Patterns on Positive Discipline

According to Alundin, a boarding school is an educational institution where students not only study, but they live and live together in the institution. Boarding schools combine students' residence in school institutions far from their homes and families with being taught religion and learning several subjects in the same place (Marsudi 2012, 44). There are several benefits to implementing a boarding school, one of which is forming an independent personality. With the boarding school system, children are accustomed to being independent, apart from that, if learning is carried out using the boarding school system, students can easily understand and implement it directly.

Disciplinary attitudes play an important role in the smooth running of the learning process, but often students see discipline as something that restricts them and makes them uncomfortable at school so that the learning process is hampered.

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Along with developments over time, there is a new theory regarding discipline, namely positive discipline developed by Jane Nelsen (Nelsen, Lott and Glenn 2000). Positive discipline provides a new perspective on discipline, where students truly realize that discipline is a necessity. Positive discipline is not about punishment or control but about teaching, education, preparation, training, regulation, developing skills by building trust, promoting self-regulation, understanding of the child, a sense of empathy and focus on solutions (J. Nelsen 2013)

From the results of a simple linear regression test using the Eviews 12 SV application, it shows that the Boarding School Learning Pattern (X) influences the Positive Discipline of Students (Y). As for the explanation of the results of the simple linear regression test, the values obtained are $B_0 = 27.927$ and $B_1 = 0.364$, so that the model obtained is $Y = 27.927 + 0.364 X$ or Boarding School Learning Pattern. The magnitude of the influence of the Boarding School Learning Pattern on the Positive Discipline of Students = 0.364 with a Probability value = 0.00. Because the Probability value (0.00) < 0.05, it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Boarding School Learning Pattern on the Positive Discipline of Students. From this model, the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the better the boarding school learning pattern, the more influence it has on positive discipline.

From the results of the partial test (t), it was found that there was a positive and significant influence of the Boarding School Learning Pattern on Students' Positive Discipline with a calculated t value of 3.48 which was greater than the t table value of 1.671 with a probability value of $0.00 < 0.05$.

Then the coefficient value obtained from data processing for the influence of the Boarding School Learning Pattern on the Positive Discipline of Students is the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.135$, this value shows that the influence of the Boarding School Learning Pattern on the Positive Discipline of Students is 13.5%, the rest is influenced consider other factors not included in the research. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between Boarding School Learning Patterns and Positive Discipline of Students. So if the Boarding School Learning Pattern is implemented with positive discipline it will have a positive influence on the learning process.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the simple linear regression test that has been carried out, it shows that the constant is 27.927, which means that the consistency value of the boarding school learning pattern is 27.927 and the regression coefficient is 0.364, which states that for every 1% addition to the value of the boarding school learning pattern, the participant's discipline is positive. students will increase by 0.364. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of boarding school learning patterns (variable X) on students' positive discipline (variable Y) is positive. and the tcount value of 3.480 is greater than the ttable value of 1.671 with a significance value of $0.00 < 0.050$. because the value of tcount > ttable and the significance value is smaller than 0.05 and it is stated that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that the boarding school learning pattern has a positive and significant effect on the positive discipline variable of students. The coefficient of determination value is 13.5%, which means that the boarding school learning pattern variable contributes 13.5% to the positive discipline variable of students. Meanwhile, the remaining 86.5% was caused by other factors.

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